

Effects of Microgravity on Bone Remodeling and Strategies for Preventing Spaceflight-Induced Osteopenia

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Introduction

Microgravity (zero-gravity) leads to decreased osteoblastic activity and increased osteoclastic resorption due to reduced mechanical loading, resulting in accelerated osteopenia, a process similar to osteoporosis and prolonged bed rest. This review aims to synthesize current data regarding the effects of microgravity on the human skeletal system and to evaluate the main strategies proposed for preventing bone mass loss during long-duration space missions.

Materials and methods

A literature review was conducted using studies indexed in PubMed and Embase between 2015-2025. Selected publications focused on clinical outcomes related to bone mineral density measurements, musculoskeletal adaptation, and the reported effectiveness of exercise, nutritional, and pharmacological countermeasures applied in operational space programs. Animal studies and techniques that are exclusively in experimental stages were excluded.

Results

Studies show a loss of bone mineral density under microgravity conditions of approximately 1–1.5% per month—10 to 15 times faster than in senile osteoporosis—predominantly affecting the lower skeleton. Resistive physical exercise using devices such as the Advanced Resistive Exercise Device (ARED) reduces this loss by approximately 50–70%, depending on the skeletal region. These measures are complemented by pharmacological interventions, particularly osteoclast inhibitors (bisphosphonates), along with adequate nutritional intake of calcium and vitamin D, contributing an additional estimated 20–30%—resulting in total bone loss of less than 1% in some missions. The combination of ARED and pharmacotherapy currently provides the best protection, although post-flight recovery remains variable.

Conclusion

Microgravity produces significant disturbances in bone homeostasis, constituting a major challenge in space medicine. While existing countermeasures substantially limit skeletal demineralization, complete prevention has not yet been achieved. Optimization of these strategies is essential for maintaining crew health during long-duration exploration missions and may also contribute valuable insights into the management of bone loss disorders on Earth.

Keywords

Spaceflight, Osteoporosis, Microgravity, Resistance Exercise